

EVALUATION OF PEEL RESISTANCE OF OUT-OF-AUTOCLAVE PREPREGS

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the peel resistance of unidirectional out-of-autoclave (OOA) prepregs tapes has been evaluated using floating roller peel tests, per standard D3167 – 10. The peel load from the tests was measured as a function of compaction load, lay-up temperature and lay-up speed. A three-factor two-level full factorial design of experiments was used to evaluate the contribution of each factor toward the overall tack resistance. The layup was carried out in a CNC milling machine, Bridgeport GX 480 using a roller assembly that was manufactured in-house. Initial observations reveal an average peel load of 170 N/m, with the highest 256 N/m recorded at higher levels of factors. Indications from the analysis suggest variation in lay-up temperature to cause significant variation in peel load values. The main factors and interaction factors contributed to ~30 % and 10% respectively of the overall peel load values.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the current age, to meet the high performance requirement set by airline companies, several OEMs are proposing futuristic designs. However, to realise them using traditional composite manufacturing techniques, it will require larger autoclaves and extensive skilled labour, which is high on capital and low on productivity. Therefore, to reduce capital expenses and improve profitability, automated lay-up techniques using robots and Out-of-Autoclave (OOA) prepregs are emerging as new technologies.

Automated Fibre Placement systems were commercially introduced towards the end of the 1980s, being described as a logical combination of automated tape lay-up (ATL) and filament winding (FW) [1, 2]. AFP system has taken over systems such as the automated tape lay-up (ATL) and filament winding (FW) and is gaining popularity in the current age. Several modifications to the ATL technique, such as the roller, material guides, controlled speed of lay-up, compaction loads, temperature, and tape tension have been made to improve the AFP process. Particular issues such as, reliability, productivity, and lay-up accuracy that arose in early AFP studies have now been resolved and current AFP machines are able to achieve lay-up speeds of up to 80m/min [3]. Indeed, the ability of the AFP process to cope with current production requirements and material configurations makes it a leading technology for future developments in the areas of smart and tailored structures across a broad range of industrial sectors.

Automated fibre placement technology for OOA prepreg consists of a fibre-processing head attached to an end-effector of a serial robot that guides and places fibre tows along a pre-defined trajectory [1]. Shape conformation to the mould surface before the vacuum consolidation is achieved by tacking the fibre tows on the mould using heat and compression simultaneously. The heat source for tacking varies from basic gas torches to more sophisticated technologies and the compression is provided by relatively soft silicon rubber rollers. The temperature and pressure are measured using sensors which is fed back into a computer numerical control (CNC) control loop to determine the lay-up compaction load, temperature and speed. The effectiveness of the system to adapt and change according to the lay-up conditions require a thorough understanding of the process and material interactions. After the lay-up on the tool or the mould is completed, the lay-up is bagged and cured in an oven under vacuum pressure. Thus, eliminating the requirement of an autoclave altogether.

Several modifications to the ATL technique, such as the roller, material guides, controlled lay-up speed, pressure, temperature, and tape tension were made to improve the AFP process. However, other material-related issues such as a short contact time, leading to insufficient compaction, flow occurring between the plies decreasing the permeability of the prepreg are still being investigated [3, 4] and a thorough understanding of the process and material interaction is still required.

In this study, the effect of changing the temperature, lay-up speed and lay-up temperature on the tack levels of OOA prepreg in terms of peel resistance has been evaluated using a full-factorial design of experiments. The factors were varied between two levels and orthogonal arrays were setup to obtain the factor formulation. Analysis based on Taguchi method has been used considered to evaluate the main and interaction factor effects on the peel load.

2 MATERIALS AND TESTING

The samples used for compression testing were prepared from a low temperature cure epoxy prepreg system, CYCOM[®] 5320-1, supplied by CYTEC Engineered Materials Inc. USA. The mechanical properties of the resin in this composite can achieve properties equal to other 177 °C (350 °F) autoclave-cured toughened epoxy prepreg systems, after a freestanding post-cure at 177°C (350°F) [5]. The T_{gel} for this system is 60 minutes at 169.8 °C and the wet T_g is 163 °C, the nominal width of the tape is 6.35 mm.

Figure 1 OOA prepreg tape being (a) laid-up on aluminium strips in a Bridgeport CNC machine (b) Measured temperature using infrared camera

The roller assembly was manufactured using tool grade aluminium and industrial grade roller. A 20 kN load cell from Omegadyne, LCM202, which was housed between the roller assembly and the tool arbour was used to measure the compaction load. An infrared camera, Fluke A-6 SC series was used to record

the lay-up temperature and a hot air gun was used as the heat source. Four test specimens were deposited on aluminium strips, per ASTM D3167 in one pass, shown in Figure 1 (a). The hot air gun was positioned away from the lay-up zone on a stand, directing the air flow on to the tape just before lay-up, Figure 1(b). The distance and the settings of the hot air gun were determined from a different set of similar experiments. Floating roller peel test fixture to determine peel resistance, as per standard ASTM D3167 [6].

3 DESIGN OF EXPERIMENTS

Compaction load, lay-up speed and lay-up temperature were considered in this work. The factors setting and their acronyms are listed in Table 2 and Table 1, respectively. A typical two-level, three-factor DoE requires 8 trials to complete the entire experimental work. An orthogonal array can be used has been considered for estimating the best material formulation needed to obtain maximum mechanical properties. The advantage of using orthogonal arrays is that it exhibits the property of orthogonality; allowing the estimation of average effects without the results being distorted by other factor effects, meaning that all the trials are unique and do not repeat. A coded design matrix has been set up with factors at their respective levels such that they are orthogonal at all times (Table 3). However, sometimes the factors influence each other and this is termed as an ‘interaction effect’ between the two factors and can be easily determined by plotting each factor against the others with respect to their levels.

Table 1 Factors and their respective codes considered in this study

Acronym	Representation
L	Compaction load (N/m)
S	Lay-up speed mm/min
T	Temperature (°C)
LS	L and S interaction
LT	L and T interaction
ST	S and T interaction
y_{1-8}	Response value
\bar{y}	Average response value (grand average)
LS, LT, ST	Average response of the factor interactions
\bar{y}_{max}	Maximum average response value

Table 2 Factors and their respective levels

Factors	Level	
	1	2
Compaction load L (kN)	0.5	1.0
Lay-up seed S (mm/min)	20	120
Temperature T (°C)	25	65

Table 3 Coded design matrix with factors at their respective levels

Trial	Factor			y (N/m)
	L	S	T	
y ₁	1	1	1	118.5
y ₂	1	1	2	180.1
y ₃	1	2	1	150.1
y ₄	1	2	2	199.1
y ₅	2	1	1	131.1
y ₆	2	1	2	214.9
y ₇	2	2	1	107.4
y ₈	2	2	2	255.9

Figure 2 Main and interaction factor contributions

To examine the contribution of each factor towards the tack resistance, each factor is plotted on either side of the grand average, which is the average value of all the trials, as shown in Figure 2. The size of the connecting line between the two levels represents the amount that factor contributes to the overall average when it is changed from low level to high level. In the same way, all the other factors are plotted.

The main factors are represented as L, S and T, and their interactions are represented as LS, LT and ST (refer Table 1 for nomenclature). If the peel load is only a function of the main factors, then the maximum attainable value would be the sum of the grand average and the positive contributions of the main factors, which can be expressed as

$$\bar{y}_{\max} = \bar{y} + (\text{L contribution}) + (\text{S contribution}) + (\text{T contribution}) \quad (1)$$

where \bar{y}_{\max} is the maximum attainable tensile modulus value and \bar{y} is the grand average and the others are as described in the Eq.(1). It is evident in Figure 2 that if all the main factors are set at higher levels, a higher peel load can be expected (first three lines). The maximum peel load considering individual factor contribution set at their higher levels is 229 N/m (from Eq.(1)), but this does not correspond to the value in Table 3 where the factors set at same levels result in a higher value, 256 N/m. Therefore, this discrepancy in average values and actual values indicate a presence of interaction between the factors.

Table 4 Values used for calculation of LS interaction effect

L	S	observed values	average
1	1	118.5	180.1
1	2	150.1	199.1
2	1	131.1	214.9
2	2	107.4	255.9

Figure 3 LS interactions effect plot, $L_2 = 1$ kN, $L_1 = 0.5$ kN, $S_1 = 20$ mm/min, $S_2 = 120$ mm/min

Interaction effects estimated in this study is established by examining the variation of each factor with respect to the mean or average value. For example, to examine the interaction effect of the factors L and S, the trials consisting of both these variables at both their levels are isolated, as shown in Table 4. As this method consists of two levels, the values of L and S will occur in two trials. Hence, the factors, L and S, when set at level 1, occur in trials y_1 and y_2 . The average response of the two factors, when set at level 1, is the average of the response values in y_1 and y_2 . Similarly, the averages of the factors at other levels calculated and plotted as seen in Figure 3.

3.1 LS interactions effect

Interaction of compaction load and lay-up speed in Figure 3 shows negative synergistic interaction between the two factors. At higher lay-up loads, the variation of lay-up speed from 20 mm/min to 120 mm/min has little change in the peel load values, seen as a relatively flat line (L_2) in Figure 3. However, at lower compaction loads, 120 mm/min seems to favour the peel load, value changing from 149 N/m at L_1S_1 to 175 N/m at L_2S_2 . This interaction effect will produce a negative effect of 4.15 N/m.

3.2 LT interactions effect

In Figure 4, antagonistic interaction between the two factors is clear due to intersection in the compaction load and temperature response traces. Higher layup temperatures produce higher peel forces irrespective of the compaction load. However, for lower temperature layup, a lower compaction load (L_1) is

preferred, since it yields a higher peel force. It is interesting in Figure 4 to see how much the lines deviates from each other while traversing from lower temperature to higher temperature. The contribution of this interaction produces an effect of 30 N/m on the overall peel load of the tape. Similar observations in [7] report the relaxation in stresses immediately after the application of load. In essence, the load to achieve better adhesion at higher temperatures is higher than at lower temperatures. This is because, the viscosity of matrix is low at higher temperatures, and the action of spreading is better achieved at that compaction load (squeezing force). Therefore, to achieve better adhesion at low temperature tacking, it is advisable to use a lower compaction forces.

Table 5 Values used for calculation of LT interaction effect

L	T	observed values		average
1	1	118.5	150.1	134.3
1	2	180.1	199.0	189.6
2	1	131.1	107.4	119.2
2	2	214.8	255.9	235.4

Figure 4 LT interaction plot $L_2 = 1$ kN, $L_1 = 0.5$ kN, $T_1 = 25$ °C, $T_2 = 65$ °C

3.3 ST interactions effect

In Figure 5, positive synergistic interactions, with the peel load increasing when the factors are set at their high levels is noticeable. The peel load irrespective of lay-up speed at lower temperature is considerably lower than at higher temperature, 13% increase in case of higher speed (S_2). The factor interaction in this case is not as prominent as LT interactions as lines do not intersect each other. The contribution of this interaction factor to the overall peel load is 6.52 N/m.

Table 6 Values used for calculation of ST interaction effect

S	T	observed values		average
1	1	118.5	131.1	124.8
1	2	180.1	214.8	197.5
2	1	150.1	107.4	128.7
2	2	199.1	255.9	227.5

Figure 5 ST interaction plot $S_1 = 20$ mm/min, $S_2 = 120$ mm/min, $T_1 = 25$ °C, $T_2 = 65$ °C

Figure 6 Half-Normal plot depicting the importance of all the factors

Effects in Figure 2 to Figure 5 show some contribution to the overall peel load of the specimen but to estimate what factors contribute significantly half-normal plots were plotted. In Figure 6 it is clear that temperature factor plays a significant role compared to the other main factor effects, and load-speed and speed-temperature interaction effects contribute substantially compared to the other interaction factor effects. It has to be noted that though speed effect does not play a significant role, it has to be considered because the factor is present in both the significantly contributing interaction factor effects. Therefore, including all the significantly contributing factor effects, results in Eq. (2).

$$\bar{y}_{\max} = \bar{y} + (\text{L contribution}) + (\text{S contribution}) + (\text{T contribution}) + (\text{LS contribution}) + (\text{LT contribution}) + (\text{ST contribution}) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Peel load} = 169.65 + 7.70 L_2 + 8.49 S_2 + 42.86 T_2 - 4.15 (LS)_2 + 15.21 (LT)_2 + 6.52 (ST)_2$$

In the correlation of actual experimental results with predicted results, shown in Figure 7 and listed in Table 7, it is evident that the Eq. (2) predicts within 10% error, with the maximum being 9% in trial y_7 , when compaction load, lay-up speed and lay-up temperature are set at levels 2, 2 and 1, respectively.

Table 7 Error in the predicted and actual values considering only two-factor effects

Trial	Factor			Experimental (N/m)	Predicted (N/m)	Absolute error (%)
	L	S	T			
y_1	1	1	1	118.5	128.2	8%
y_2	1	1	2	180.1	170.4	5%
y_3	1	2	1	150.1	140.4	6%
y_4	1	2	2	199.1	208.8	5%
y_5	2	1	1	131.1	121.5	7%
y_6	2	1	2	214.8	211.9	1%
y_7	2	2	1	107.4	117.1	9%
y_8	2	2	2	255.9	246.3	3%

Figure 7 Correlation of actual experimental results with predicted results at respective trial order

5 SUMMARY

Based on results of the DoE analysis, the layup temperature has the greatest influence in determining the resulting peel force. Significant antagonistic interactions between the compaction load and temperature indicate an application of compaction higher load on the tapes that are deposited at 65 °C. The load-speed interaction effect is of least significance, followed by the speed-temperature effect.

The load-speed interaction effect is of least significance, followed by the speed-temperature effect. In essence, the peel force is virtually independent of load-speed and speed-temperature factor interactions. For a faster layup rate, it is suggested to set load and temperature factors to 1 kN and 65 °C respectively, to yield a peel force of 246 N/m at 120 mm/min. Experimental tests carried out at the predicted factor settings agree well with the analysis, a procedure that yielded a peel force of 256 N/m with a standard deviation of 25 N/m.

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